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Individuals with Basic Digital Skills in the Regions of Italy

Between 2014 and 2021 they increased by 31.12%

Eurostat within the DESI metrics calculates the value of individuals with basic digital skills. Digital skills are defined as the following activities, namely "Information Skills", "Communication Skills", "Problem Solving Skills", "Software Skills". The level is considered basic if people have one of the four competencies indicated.

Ranking of Italian regions by value of individuals with basic digital skills in 2021. Emilia Romagna and Trentino Alto Adige are in first place by value of basic digital skills with an amount of 79.49, followed by Lombardy, Veneto, Friuli Venezia Giulia and Lazio with an amount of 78.13. The ranking is closed by Molise, Puglia and Calabria with an amount of 64.54 and Sicily with an amount of 63.18.

Ranking of European countries by value of the percentage change in the value of individuals with basic digital skills between 2014 and 2021. Basilicata is in first place by value of the percentage change in the presence of individuals with basic digital skills with an amount of + 78.22% equal to an amount of 28.92, followed by Campania with an amount of 65.82% equal to an amount of 26.7 units and by Molise with an amount of 52.38% equal to an amount of 22.19 units. In the middle of the ranking we find Tuscany with an amount of 27.36% equal to an amount of 16.49 units, followed by Valle d'Aosta with an amount of 25.10% equal to an amount of 15.13 units and Lazio with an amount of 22.34% equal to an amount of 14.27 units. The classification is closed by Veneto with an amount of 15.84% equal to an amount of 10.68 units, followed by Trentino Alto Adige with an amount of 13.33% equal to an amount of 9.35 units and by Lombardy with a amount of 12.84% equal to an amount of 8.89 units. Overall, between 2014 and 2021, the value of people with basic digital skills grew by an amount equal to 31.12%, equal to an amount of 16 units.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. A clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient is presented below. Two clusters are therefore identified, namely:

- Cluster 1: Marche, Lazio, Sardinia, Veneto, Lombardy, Tuscany, Emilia Romagna, Trentino Alto Adige, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Umbria, Piedmont, Liguria, Abruzzo;
- Cluster 2: Campania, Sicily, Calabria, Puglia, Molise, Basilicata, Valle d'Aosta.

From the point of view of the median of the clusters, it appears that the value of cluster 1-C1 is equal to an amount of 76.77 while the value of cluster 2-C2 is equal to an amount of 64.54 units. From a geographical point of view, there is an evident contrast between the Centre-North, with high levels of presence of individuals with basic digital skills, and the South with low levels of basic digital skills. From this point of view it is necessary to consider that by analyzing the trend of the variables from the point of view of the macro-regions, i.e. the Centre, the North and the South, the convergence of

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the Center and the North and the divergence of the South with respect to the more advanced regions is evident. In fact, from a strictly geographical point of view, it appears that the southern regions grew on average by 44.29% between 2014 and 2021, while the central regions grew by 22.45% and the northern regions by 19.01%. However, although the regions of the South have recovered a lot in terms of the presence of individuals with basic digital skills, the gap between the Centre-North and the South is still very evident.

Network analysis with Euclidean distance. A network analysis with Euclidean distance is presented below. A complex network structure is identified, namely:

- Sardinia has a connection with Tuscany for an amount of 0.44 units;
- Tuscany has a connection with Sardinia for an amount of 0.44 units, with the Marche for an amount of 0.49 units, and with Lazio for an amount of 0.44 units;
- The Marche have a connection with Tuscany for an amount of 0.49 units, with Lazio for an amount of 0.52 units;
- Lazio has a connection with Tuscany for an amount of 0.44 units, with the Marche for a value of 0.52 units and with Veneto for an amount of 0.48 units;
- Veneto has a connection with Lazio for an amount of 0.48 units.

Obviously the presence of a network analysis does not identify cause-effect relationships but rather highlights the common dynamics between the variables and the propagation effects. That is, for example, if the value of individuals with basic digital skills grows in the Marche then it can spread to Tuscany and Lazio.

Machine Learning and Predictions. Below is a comparison of eight different algorithms for predicting the future value of individuals with basic digital skills. The algorithms are compared according to the maximization of the R-Squared and the minimization of the statistical errors. The algorithms were trained with 70% of the data while the remaining 30% of the data was used for prediction. The ordering of the algorithms based on their predictive performance is identified below, namely:

- ANN-Artificial Neural Network with a payoff value of 4;
- Simple Regression Tree with a payoff value of 8;
- PNN-Probabilistic Neural Network with a payoff value of 14;
- Tree Ensemble Regression with a payoff value of 19;
- Random Forest Regression and Linear Regression with a payoff value of 22;
- Polynomial Regression with a payoff value equal to 23;
- Gradient Boosted Trees Regression with a payoff value of 32.

Through the application of the ANN the following changes are predicted, namely:

- Puglia with a positive variation equal to an amount of 268.08%;
- Friuli Venezia Giulia with a negative variation equal to an amount of -11.86%;
- Emilia Romagna with a negative change equal to an amount of 10.13%;
- Marche with a positive change equal to an amount of 3.88%;
- Lazio with a negative change equal to an amount of -9.14%.

On average, the value of the predictions for the regions analyzed is predicted to grow by a value equal to 48.16%.

Conclusions. The value of people who have basic digital skills grew in all Italian regions between 2014 and 2021. There is a contrast between Central-Northern Italy and Southern Italy with a re-proposition of the socio-economic gap in a digital version. Between 2014 and 2021, the growth rate of basic digital skills in the South was higher than in the Centre-North, even if significant differences persist. The growth of basic digital skills is necessary to support the knowledge economy, technological innovation, digitization and improve human capital. Basic digital skills are necessary not only to carry out work activities but also to make the most of the services offered by the public administration and private companies. In fact, the rate of innovativeness of consumers and citizens is the element that supports digitization at a regional, macro-regional and national level.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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Appendix

Risultati Statistici Machine Learning					
	ANN	PNN	Gradient Boosted Trees Regression	Random Forest Regression	
R^2	0,983446696	0,875447387	0,067426016	0,877600407	
mean absolute error	0,034131252	0,086363636	0,275051117	0,097008138	
mean squared error	0,002864258	0,013181818	0,12664585	0,021793928	
root mean squared error	0,053518764	0,114812099	0,355873362	0,147627665	
	Tree Ensemble Regression	Linear Regression	Polynomial Regression	Simple Regression Tree	
R^2	0,869663294	0,802473748	0,869663294	0,935184325	
mean absolute error	0,109921882	0,085164739	0,109921882	0,079545455	
mean squared error	0,017322915	0,018874731	0,017322915	0,010014922	
root mean squared error	0,131616545	0,137385337	0,131616545	0,100074582	

Algoritmo	R^2	MAE	MSE	RMSE	TOTALE
<i>ANN</i>	1	1	1	1	4
<i>Simple Regression Tree</i>	2	2	2	2	8
<i>PNN</i>	4	4	3	3	14
<i>Tree Ensemble Regression</i>	5	6	4	4	19
<i>Random Forest Regression</i>	3	5	7	7	22
<i>Linear Regression</i>	7	3	6	6	22
<i>Polynomial Regression</i>	6	7	5	5	23
<i>Gradient Boosted Trees Regression</i>	8	8	8	8	32

Rank	Regione	Var Ass	Var Per	Rank	Regione	Var Ass	Var Per
1	<i>Basilicata</i>	28,92	78,22	11	<i>Lazio</i>	14,27	22,34
2	<i>Campania</i>	26,7	65,82	12	<i>Umbria</i>	12,91	20,21
3	<i>Molise</i>	22,19	52,38	13	<i>Marche</i>	12,91	20,21
4	<i>Calabria</i>	22,19	52,38	14	<i>Liguria</i>	11,98	19,30
5	<i>Abruzzo</i>	22,74	44,30	15	<i>Friuli-Venezia Giulia</i>	12,47	19,00
6	<i>Puglia</i>	16,81	35,21	16	<i>Emilia-Romagna</i>	12,04	17,85
7	<i>Piemonte</i>	17,79	32,41	17	<i>Sardegna</i>	10,19	15,95
8	<i>Sicilia</i>	15,45	32,36	18	<i>Veneto</i>	10,68	15,84
9	<i>Toscana</i>	16,49	27,36	19	<i>Trentino Alto Adige</i>	9,35	13,33
10	<i>Valle d'Aosta</i>	15,13	25,10	20	<i>Lombardia</i>	8,89	12,84

Rank	Regione	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
1	<i>Piemonte</i>	★ 54,90	★ 54,14	★ 58,49	★ 58,49	★ 59,77	★ 59,74	★ 59,68	★ 72,70
2	<i>Valle d'Aosta</i>	★ 60,28	★ 57,04	★ 54,32	★ 54,32	★ 55,93	★ 52,25	★ 54,93	★ 75,41
3	<i>Liguria</i>	★ 62,07	★ 52,69	★ 54,32	★ 54,32	★ 57,21	★ 60,99	★ 60,86	★ 74,06
4	<i>Lombardia</i>	★ 69,24	★ 62,84	★ 64,04	★ 64,04	★ 64,89	★ 63,48	★ 62,05	★ 78,13
5	<i>Abruzzo</i>	★ 51,32	★ 59,94	★ 55,71	★ 55,71	★ 59,77	★ 60,99	★ 57,30	★ 74,06
6	<i>Molise</i>	★ 42,36	★ 45,44	★ 52,93	★ 52,93	★ 53,37	★ 53,50	★ 45,42	★ 64,54
7	<i>Campania</i>	★ 40,56	★ 46,89	★ 48,77	★ 48,77	★ 49,53	★ 54,75	★ 51,36	★ 67,26
8	<i>Puglia</i>	★ 47,73	★ 46,89	★ 51,55	★ 51,55	★ 49,53	★ 52,25	★ 51,36	★ 64,54
9	<i>Basilicata</i>	★ 36,98	★ 54,14	★ 44,60	★ 44,60	★ 49,53	★ 51,00	★ 52,55	★ 65,90
10	<i>Calabria</i>	★ 42,36	★ 45,44	★ 44,60	★ 44,60	★ 46,97	★ 46,01	★ 46,61	★ 64,54
11	<i>Sicilia</i>	★ 47,73	★ 43,99	★ 45,99	★ 45,99	★ 48,25	★ 52,25	★ 47,80	★ 63,18
12	<i>Sardegna</i>	★ 63,87	★ 61,39	★ 64,04	★ 64,04	★ 61,05	★ 58,49	★ 62,05	★ 74,06
13	<i>Veneto</i>	★ 67,45	★ 67,19	★ 61,27	★ 61,27	★ 62,33	★ 60,99	★ 62,05	★ 78,13
14	<i>Friuli-Venezia Giulia</i>	★ 65,66	★ 61,39	★ 66,82	★ 66,82	★ 62,33	★ 59,74	★ 57,30	★ 78,13
15	<i>Emilia-Romagna</i>	★ 67,45	★ 68,64	★ 66,82	★ 66,82	★ 63,61	★ 63,48	★ 64,43	★ 79,49
16	<i>Toscana</i>	★ 60,28	★ 64,29	★ 62,65	★ 62,65	★ 61,05	★ 59,74	★ 62,05	★ 76,77
17	<i>Umbria</i>	★ 63,87	★ 65,74	★ 58,49	★ 58,49	★ 61,05	★ 58,49	★ 58,49	★ 76,77
18	<i>Marche</i>	★ 63,87	★ 64,29	★ 62,65	★ 62,65	★ 59,77	★ 62,23	★ 63,24	★ 76,77
19	<i>Lazio</i>	★ 63,87	★ 62,84	★ 61,27	★ 61,27	★ 62,33	★ 60,99	★ 60,86	★ 78,13
20	<i>Trentino Alto Adige</i>	★ 70,14	★ 65,01	★ 68,21	★ 68,21	★ 61,05	★ 60,99	★ 62,05	★ 79,49